

Deliverable 6.1

JCOM community page plan and technical requirements

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Introduction

The overall objective of RETHINK is to provide recommendations and guidelines to maintain and improve the quality of interactions in the new science communication landscape. RETHINK aims to provide support to re-examine and re-orientate science communication across Europe. Over the course of the project, a wide variety of actors will be mobilized and several types of data will be collected and used.

Deliverable 6.2 *JCOM community page plan and technical requirements* is the third deliverable of Work Package 6 “ENGAGE: communication and dissemination”, led by SISSA Medialab. It presents the iterative process that led to the creation of the RETHINK-JCOM community page, from its first conceptualization up to the implementation of feedback from Rethinkerspaces representatives. It also provide information on how we plan to make the RETHINK-JCOM community page grow and engage a wide community.

RETHINK overview

Open and productive interactions between science and society are vital for a healthy democracy. The relationship between science and the rest of society is a crucial aspect of how our society develops and addresses societal challenges such as food security and climate change. Fruitful interactions between science and society are not straightforward, as recent controversies have shown.

We need an approach to science communication that is able to nurture interactions between science and society in an open and reflexive way. However, the science communication landscape itself is undergoing deep and fundamental changes due to two interrelated changes.

First, the boundaries between science and society have become blurred. Interactions and interfaces between science and other fields in society such as economics, politics, art and culture have become more numerous and diverse. Second, digitalization has revolutionized the science communication landscape. It has fundamentally changed how scientists; other R&I stakeholders and a variety of publics interact and communicate.

These developments require us to rethink the newly emerging science communication landscape to ensure the quality of interactions between the actors involved. In the context of emerging digital media, it has become relatively easy to disregard scientific evidence as ‘just another opinion’. At the same time, at least part of the scientific community still struggles with the lingering yet false assumption that deficits in public knowledge (referred to as the ‘deficit model’) are the central factor in social conflicts and controversies about science, while in fact underlying interests, moral values and cultural beliefs have a much larger role in shaping public views about science.

It is a time of great opportunity to open science and create meaningful connections with society if the right conditions are created. The RETHINK project encompasses today’s key manifestations of science communication with a particular focus on the digital sphere where scientists, science communicators and various publics exchange information, ideas and concerns and where challenges, but also opportunities exist to open up science and form meaningful connections.

Aim and approach of RETHINK

How can the theory and practice of science communication contribute to a productive relationship between science and society, supporting the opening up of research and innovation practices whilst simultaneously maintaining and improving the quality of interactions amongst the actors involved? Professional science communicators have always been key catalysts of meaningful interactions at the interface between science and society, building bridges between experts, policymakers and society as a whole. How can they continue to play this vital role in the newly emerging landscape bringing together a seemingly endless variety of actors, activities, communicative spaces and sensemaking practices?

Against this backdrop, the RETHINK project aspires to rethink science communication, both its theory and practice, to accommodate the major challenges to the individual and collective process of making sense about science. We focus on everyday practices of making sense about science and recognize that sense-making is not only about basic scientific knowledge, but also about a range of other aspects, such as how science works, the limits of scientific knowledge, the importance of economic, social, political and ethical dimensions and the legitimacy of a variety of values and perspectives that are present in the public conversation about science. Scientific understanding may provide part of the solution to a social problem, but not all of it. An open and reflexive approach to the complexities of sensemaking is crucial to address social conflicts and controversies arising in the interaction between science and society. Even if past years have seen a growing number of participation mechanisms and deliberative forums mushroom, these coexist with a big number of European citizens that rely on mediated communication to make sense about science in relation to social issues.

With these notions in mind, a guiding principle of RETHINK is that the contextual knowledge of citizens across the EU should play a vital role in shaping future scientific and technological developments and the sharing of this knowledge should be facilitated. We eventually aim to improve the quality of interactions between science and society by providing concrete recommendations and training resources for nurturing open and reflexive science-society interfaces. The following diagram explains how the project is structured and how it works towards its final goal “A European science communication ecosystem that is open, inclusive, reflexive and adaptive”.

The context

Before focusing on the development process of the RETHINK-JCOM community page, we provide some information on JCOM, its community of scicomm researchers and practitioners, as well as what led to the idea of creating a community page linked to the journal.

JCOM – Journal of Science Communication

30/09/2019 Comment

The need for feminist approaches to science communication

by Bruce Lewenstein

As science communication develops as a field of both practice and research, it needs to address issues of equity, diversity, and inclusion across a wide range, including race, power, class, gender. Doing so will require deeper understanding of conceptual work and practical activities that address those issues. This brief...

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JCOM is an open access peer reviewed journal focused on science communication. The journal covers a broad range of issues pertinent to science communication and public engagement with STEM, including citizen science as well as environmental and health communication, where these relate to communication of research.

JCOM caters for scholars coming from sociology of science, science and technology studies, media and communication, museums studies and other disciplinary perspectives. By doing so, we seek to encourage interdisciplinary exchange in the

study of today's complex knowledge societies and the role of publics and scientists in the development of new knowledge.

JCOM publishes research that explores a wide range of issues pertinent to the science communication community, including: issues in communication between science and citizens and within the scientific community itself; challenges arising when models for theoretical analysis or practical means to popularize science are used; the changing relation between science and social institutions; and the informative, pedagogical, interpretative and political dimensions of science communication.

JCOM contributes to forging a common identity for scholars across disciplines by adopting a policy of free circulation of information. JCOM is also a platform where distant and sometimes fragmented communities can meet: academic scholars, journalists, museum operators, and scientists who live and work in fields where theoretical reflection and concrete action are strongly intertwined.

JCOM has published research relevant to both the academic and practitioner communities engaged in science communication since 2002. In addition to research papers, JCOM also publishes invited thematic commentaries, essays, practice insights, reviews and letters.

JCOM adopts a Creative Commons licensing policy, giving the community the opportunity to freely spread contents under a Creative Commons 4.0 by-nc-nd license. The journal does not apply any article processing or submission charge.

JCOM had over 100.000 page visits in 2018, and almost 95.000 downloads of papers published open access in the journal. Most of JCOM visitors and authors are based in Europe and North America, with a raising number of users also from China, India and Brazil. JCOM is indexed in Scopus (CiteScore in 2018: 0,81). Since 2018, Sissa Medialab also publishes JCOM AL, a regional version of JCOM focused on Latin America, with papers in Spanish and in Portuguese.

The JCOM community

JCOM receives every year almost 200 submissions from authors all over the world. All submitted contributions, if accepted, undergo a double-blind peer review process. JCOM is also active on social media, both on Facebook (with over 3.700 followers) and on Twitter (1.500 followers).

JCOM regularly publishes “special issues” and sets of commentaries, typically organised by a guest Editorial Board or Editorial Advisory Board, that cover topical issues through a collection of contributions. Recent special issues and sets of commentaries include:

- The need for feminist approaches to science communication
- Communication at the Intersection of Science and Politics
- User Experience of Digital Technologies in Citizen Science
- History of Science Communication
- Citizen Science

Overall, JCOM has a very active community of Editors, contributors and supporters, thanks to the vast range of topics it focuses on, as well as the fact of being the main (and one of the very few) open access journals in the field of science communication. Several authors publish more than once in JCOM. In past surveys, JCOM authors have expressed the need for some type of support or interaction around the research they publish in JCOM. Feedback on research published there is often shared either on social media channels, or most often by getting in touch directly with the writers. JCOM authors would benefit from structured ways of interaction.

The need for a RETHINK-JCOM community page

The main aim of the RETHINK-JCOM community page is to allow for the sharing, testing and collecting of feedback on project outcomes from JCOM visitors, authors and readers, with a fully open access approach. The RETHINK-JCOM community page is therefore specifically dedicated to various forms of interaction between the RETHINK project partners and JCOM users. This community page will serve as a forum for the validation of the project strategy and expected outcomes and impacts, making use of community tools to collect feedback and contribution from the vast variety of JCOM users and visitors. The involvement of relevant end-users and stakeholders through the JCOM community will also represent an ideal test bed for conducting activities aimed at the collection of feedback and validation of the strategic approaches adopted throughout the project. All project academic outcomes (papers, etc.) will also be published open access on JCOM (undergoing the standard peer-review process in the case of papers), along with JCOM-branded essays and sets of commentaries. The RETHINK-JCOM community page will therefore allow for:

- Foster several types of interaction around project outcomes, mostly research papers and deliverables, but also research processes, training modules, recommendations, etc.
- Support the activities of the Rethinkerspaces within their own countries, in particular by creating an appealing and easy to use online environment that they can use to engage local members, communicate with them, promote activities, etc.
- Stimulate JCOM authors to not only get engaged in RETHINK activities (surveys, forum, etc.) but also to use the community page as a mean of discussion of the research they conduct, research questions, collect feedback etc.
- Promote RETHINK project activities and outcomes.

The process

The creation of the RETHINK-JCOM community page has developed over three main phases:

- Finding the right software: several options have been considered, leading to the choice of what we consider to be the best fit for the aims of the community page;
- Testing of the chosen software: staff at Sissa Medialab has tested various functionalities of the chosen provider, in order to best adapt them to the page needs;
- Setting-up and further feedback: staff at Sissa Medialab has created the community page, presented it to Rethinkerspaces leaders at a meeting in Brussels, and collect feedback on how it can best serve their needs.

Disqus and Discourse

The main choice in the creation process of the RETHINK-JCOM community page has been to decide whether it should have been implemented within the JCOM website, or as an external feature. The first two options we have tested allowed for implementation of community features within JCOM, but with a very limited set of options and a not so appealing interface.

The first option we have explored is Disqus (). Disqus is a worldwide blog comment hosting service for web sites and online communities that use a networked platform. The company's platform includes various features, such as social integration, social networking, user profiles, spam and moderation tools, analytics, email notifications, and mobile commenting.

The second option explored is Discourse (<https://discourse.sissamedialab.it/>). Discourse is an open source Internet forum and mailing list management software application founded in 2013. From a usability perspective, Discourse breaks with existing forum software by including features recently popularized by large social networks, such as infinite scrolling, live updates, expanding links, and drag and drop attachments.[6] However, the stated goals of the project are social rather than technical, to improve online discussion quality through improved forum software.

Main shortcomings of both options:

- The interface of both services is very basic, allowing for commenting on papers published in the journal, and to have a separate forum for discussion of topics. Most project partners did not like the look and feel of the interface, which does not allow for personalization or refinement, and only shows a list of discussion topics and nothing else.
- Limited functionalities: in our view, comments and forum are not enough in order to support a community building process, as users will want to do more than just commenting.

Ning

After testing Disqus and Discourse, we then explored options that could not be integrated within the JCOM website, but that would allow for a real support of a community engagement process, as well as be used by the Rethinkerspaces. We set up two test pages, one on Mighty Networks and one on Ning.

Mighty Networks is a software-as-a-service platform (SaaS) for creators, niche entrepreneurs, and businesses to bring together content, online classes, community, and subscriptions all in one place—with your brand front and center.

Ning is an online platform for people and organizations to create custom social networks. Ning was co-founded by Marc Andreessen and Gina Bianchini and launched in October 2005. By June 2011 there were over 90,000 social websites running on the Ning Platform.

Both have very similar functionalities and similar pricing schemes. During several days we tested both community pages, getting to the conclusion that Ning would be the best choice, as it allowed for more features and personalization. Besides this, Sissa Medialab staff already has extensive experience in the management of Ning community pages, as in the past it was in charge of the creation of the Pilots community page, dedicated to science explainers working in science centres and museums all over Europe, which was active during several years.

When choosing the provider for the community page, we have also looked at privacy issues, making sure that the data collection process would be in line with GDPR requirements as well as data management guidelines adopted by the RETHINK project.

The RETHINK-JCOM community page

Following a few rounds of testing, the RETHINK-JCOM community page has been up and running since mid-September 2019, at the address <http://community.rethinkscicomm.eu>:

The community page is currently composed of the following sections:

- Homepage: the homepage provides an overview of recent posts, a short description and a link to the JCOM page, Twitter widgets of both the JCOM and RETHINK Twitter accounts, an overview of recent activities happening in the community, as well as a showcase of photos and videos shared in discussions.
- Profile page: this is the page where registered users can check their profile, interact with other users, see their latest activities of the communities they belong to, etc.
- Forum: the forum will contain all RETHINK ongoing discussions. This area is accessible by all visitors, but only registered users can comment or launch a new discussion.
- Events: this is where we promote upcoming events, such as a Rethinkerspace workshop or RETHINK participating at conferences. Events can be both public, therefore visible by all visitors, or private, therefore visible only by a selected group of users.

- Rethinkerspaces: these are specific community spaces for each of the seven national Rethinkerspaces, that have launched their activities in the last couple of months. Specific Rethinkerspaces areas are accessible only to members of the national group of experts that is being set up in each country. Rethinkerspaces leaders will invite members of their groups to register on the platform, and promote the use of it for interactions, such as surveys, discussions, organization of events, sharing of workshop outcomes, etc.

Visitors who want to become active members of the community have to register by providing basic data (name, last name, email address and country of residence). Approval of new members is taken care of by the page administrators at Sissa Medialab. Once users have created their own profile, they can be assigned to a specific Rethinkerspace (according to their country of residence) if they wish show. This will allow them to access the ongoing activities within the Rethinkerspaces groups.

Testing of the RETHINK-JCOM community page with Rethinkerspaces

The first Rethinkerspaces training, held in Brussels on 23 and 24 September 2019, represented a great opportunity to collect feedback from project partners and Rethinkerspaces' leaders on their envisaged usage of the community page. Suggestions collected so far include:

- Rethinkerspaces need to be supported by a digital environment that is easy to use, flexible and doesn't require too many steps to access relevant information, as this would make users less motivated to use it.
- Rethinkerspaces will use their community environment in their local language, while the main overall forum will be entirely in English.
- Rethinkerspaces agree that the specific national community areas should only be visible and accessible to their community members. This would be beneficial to ongoing research processes, and also make users more at ease to use the tools while not feeling observed by external visitors. Therefore the Rethinkerspaces will remain private, at least while the Rethinkerspaces are being built and research activities are ongoing.
- Rethinkerspaces leaders will take care of promoting the community page to their local members, supporting them in the registration process, as well as facilitate all local interactions within the community.

- All Rethinkerspaces will share key moments of their activities (such as workshops, etc.) on their community pages as well as the Events section (including, when possible, photos, videos, etc.), in order to share and disseminate to a broader community.

Sissa Medialab staff is currently working on implementing these suggestions.

Community engagement plan

Rethinkerspaces

As mentioned before, the involvement of relevant end-users and stakeholders through the JCOM community will represent an ideal test bed for conducting activities aimed at the collection of feedback and validation of the strategic approaches adopted throughout the project.

The RETHINK-JCOM community page is at the moment still lacking contents: most of RETHINK research outcomes are not finalized yet, as their delivery date is from M12 on. It would not make sense yet to promote the RETHINK-JCOM community page to JCOM users and authors while no contents are being shared and discussed there yet. Therefore, we suggest that the Rethinkerspaces are key to the development of the RETHINK-JCOM community page in the upcoming months. The community page can strongly support their local community engagement plan, their local activities, and the promotion of what they are doing. The Rethinkerspaces are therefore our key target audience for the first few months of life of the RETHINK-JCOM community page. It has been very beneficial to have the opportunity to show the community page to leaders of the Rethinkerspaces in Brussels, and it will be crucial to build upon the feedback they have provided, as well as to regularly check on their level of satisfaction with the features of their community pages, support them in using their functionalities, and in managing to get community members to use it.

Sissa Medialab staff will regularly run feedback collection processes with the Rethinkerspaces to monitor how they are using (or planning to use) their national pages on the RETHINK-JCOM community page.

The #scicomm community

Although the RETHINK project will draw on existing communities of scicomm researchers and practitioners, such as the authors and visitors of JCOM, we will essentially be building a new online community of users. In order to do so effectively, our initial focus will be on:

1. **Developing a core group of user community members.** It is important to focus at first on developing a core small group of active platform users, in our case the Rethinkerspaces. We will spend time with each of them (those leading the Rethinkerspaces). We will make the community of users part of something they're invested in, and be sure that by the time we launch the RETHINK-JCOM community page to a wider public we have a dedicated group of people who are keen to participate.
2. **Sustaining momentum.** An online community with a low level of activity dies very quickly. We are planning out the first few weeks of our community so that its activity steadily increases. The question we will address by doing so is, how are we going to either secure more of the community page user's time or recruit more community page users?
3. **Appealing to a strong self-interest.** In order for the RETHINK-JCOM community page to be successful, we need to develop strong appeals to the self-interests of community members. Our members are more likely than usual to be interested in supporting the mission of the community page to explore current developments in science communication, and to be genuinely interested in the development of new tools, training modules and recommendations to address existing gaps, but we can't rely on that alone. We must also recognise that the users of our community page will have career-oriented reputations as well, to be seen as leaders in the field, and valuable contributors to the state of the art of science communication. We therefore need to ensure that active online community members are recognised for their talents/knowledge/skills amongst their peers.
4. **Encouraging a sense of ownership.** Take a co-creative approach to both the community page design, as well as the mapping and gathering of research outcomes. Encourage our community members to feel a deeper stake in the success of the community page through their own involvement in the early stages. Acknowledge key contributions to show the value added of those contributing actively, reward their input, but more importantly deepen their sense of ownership further.
5. **Persuading our wider target audience to make a second visit.** Raising awareness amongst our wider target audience groups (i.e. the scicomm community at large, beyond the Rethinkerspaces) will be fairly straightforward, and will lead to good initial traffic. But that second visit is much harder. What are we going to ask a visitor to do in their first visit to ensure they return?

6. **Concentrating activity.** We will be following strict release planning for all new elements and functionalities on the community page, to keep the activity concentrated in specific areas. This creates an active atmosphere, makes sure new sections are well-populated before they launch, and ensures unused features aren't indicating a quiet site.

As soon as RETHINK research outcomes will be available for discussion, administrators of the RETHINK-JCOM community page will discuss with project partners how to successfully set up thematic discussions, as well as plan how to promote them through JCOM social media channels, newsletter, etc. The RETHINK-JCOM community page will also be presented at conferences and events.

